

PRESS RELEASE

Delft, Netherlands – May 22nd, 2024 –

The [SPATIAL](#) (Security and Privacy Accountable Technology Innovations, Algorithms, and Machine Learning) project, a pioneering initiative, is set to culminate with a dynamic final event on July 1st 2024, hosted by TU Delft. This final event, “Guiding Light in the AI Landscape: Illuminating the Path to a Trustworthy AI Ecosystem”, marks a significant milestone in the project's journey, showcasing its groundbreaking contributions to spatial planning and technology impact assessment.

Held at the Faculty of Technology, Policy & Management in TU Delft, the final event invites participants from academic institutions and industry partners to discuss the present and future of Trustworthy AI, build their networks, and present their own research in poster sessions.

Dr Aaron Ding, Coordinator and Research Director of SPATIAL and director of CPI Lab at TU Delft, expressed enthusiasm about the final event, stating, "I welcome you with great pleasure to join the culminating final event of the SPATIAL project. It is not just to celebrate the conclusion of a project journey but to acknowledge the hard work, innovative ideas, and collaborative spirit that have brought us to this point. Look forward to greeting you soon!"

The logistic details are as follows:

- **July 1st:** Faculty of Technology, Policy & Management TU Delft, Jaffalaan 5, 2628BX, Delft, Netherlands. **(From 10:00 AM -17:00 PM CET).**

Please visit the SPATIAL Project Website [SPATIAL Final Event in Delft – SPATIAL H2020 \(spatial-h2020.eu\)](#) for registration and further information.

About SPATIAL Project:

SPATIAL is a European-funded project that tackles the identified gaps in data issues and black-box AI by designing and developing resilient, accountable metrics, privacy-preserving methods, verification tools, and system solutions that are critical building blocks for trustworthy AI in ICT systems and cybersecurity.

For press and media inquiries, please contact Blanca Arregui, Chief Marketing Officer at the SPATIAL project. blanca@australo.org.